

REVOLUTIONIZING ESP WITH ADAPTED AUTHENTIC MATERIALS: CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

Kurbanova Husniya Shuhrat qizi

Guliston davlat universiteti tayanch doktoranti

husniyakurbanova20@gmail.com

Abstract. The greatest problem for an ESP instructor is to choose materials relevant to the learners' linguistic skills and interests. It must be noted that even though all of them have the same objectives as regards learning in ESP courses, they are generally quite heterogeneous with regard to their ages, language skills, and professions. Considering the educational context of Uzbekistan, the question of finding suitable sources of learning for a non-philology student of different communities becomes in fact a very puzzling issue. It has become common practice for students' education to be based on authentic sources, contemporary and real ones that can be relevant to certain time. While some of such authentic materials are necessary for students' learning, they should be selected and modified with caution. In line with these challenges, it is suggested that different artificial intelligence tools be applied.

Key words: ESP, authentic material, selecting material, technological tools, natural texts, CEFR, text adapter, teaching model.

Introduction. It is well known that reading instructions in EAP classes are usually boring and monotonous. Students are often reluctant to participate in reading sessions because the texts in their textbooks and modules don't spark any interest, or meet their needs and don't appeal to their wants. Reading, as a Nunan says, is a task that involves the considerable degree of integration as the student first has to

activate information he already knows about an area before interpreting new information that is presented in the text. The researcher assumes that in order to motivate students and help them to learn English, the adoption of such other media or authentic materials will render the entire process of learning more interesting and will assist in improving their English vocabulary. It is indeed the resources that are used for the study that serve as the basis of the concepts that students are taught.

The ESP learning process employs either adjusting in-house materials or using materials already available. When developing an ESP course, the first issue is to find, select and adapt commercial materials if such materials exist. In fact, using ready-made materials saves the course instructor time and energy and is carried out throughout the teaching process. In an ESP situation, the instructor has to find a commercially available textbook for the class. They may find that the organizational difference means that they have to change how they think about how US textbooks are organized. This means that the textbook salesmen sometimes make more sense than subject experts among the instructor of courses. Where the approaches have remained broader, there are testimonies of the effectiveness of the approaches. In such cases where the topic covered is not particularly relevant to the course a suitable substitution is to move the students into a different group. “An ESP teacher initially selects from existing ready-made materials. Only after exhausting all other possibilities for presenting materials should the development of specialized materials be considered”.

The ESP instructor only needs to choose the best of the hundreds of learning resources that are available globally. Choosing a coursebook has the primary benefit of saving the instructor time and effort when generating fresh content. The fact that a coursebook frequently includes extra materials like instructor guides, student supplemental materials, self-study materials, and even audio and video resources is an added advantage. When choosing a coursebook, it is crucial to make sure that it supports each step of the teaching and learning process. However, teachers rarely

use supplemental materials and frequently grow unduly dependent on coursebooks. Swales points out that "A book chosen for an ESP course may initially be necessary, but it should be abandoned as soon as possible".

Since a single coursebook is unlikely to satisfy every student's demand, the instructor frequently needs to employ other resources. Furthermore, it is frequently required to modify pre-made materials because of a variety of reasons, including the cultural backgrounds of the pupils. When expressing their knowledge and experiences, some writers adopt a conservative stance, and as time passes, the techniques and tools they employ become outdated. A creative and seasoned teacher would modify these materials to fit their own teaching style rather than mindlessly adopting them. However, in order to accomplish specific lexical and structural objectives, some teachers make coursebooks artificial by simplifying texts, changing vocabulary, or changing content. Although using non-authentic materials in ESP lessons can produce positive benefits, they deviate from reality.

Literature review. The use of authentic reading materials in EAP classrooms. In the literature on English for Specific Purposes (ESP), there has been much discussion on whether or not the materials chosen for ESP classes should be authentic. ESP teachers are increasingly favoring authentic materials over non-authentic ones in recent years. They contend that rather than being produced with a particular educational goal in mind, texts ought to be drawn from authentic sources. These resources organically bridge the gap between the virtual classroom setting and the real world, where the language being learned is actively utilized. Reppen pointed out that "teachers preferred authentic materials over the language examples they prepared themselves in lessons, as authentic materials draw from natural texts".

Adapting Reading Materials for Non-Philological Students. When the demands and objectives of the lesson are not met by the learning resources, the existing materials are adapted. In order to make materials appropriate for students, Tomlinson supports their modification. The reading text's linguistic complexity must

be assessed and filtered by ESP teachers. To satisfy the standards for readability and comprehension, the original text frequently needs to be modified by changing the level of linguistic complexity. Technological techniques make it possible to adjust reading materials by identifying linguistic elements that need adaptation, modifying texts to suit numerous levels, analyzing typical text corpora in seconds, and providing accurate quantitative data on text difficulty indices. This enables educators to swiftly modify instructional materials. Text complexity may now be tracked with tools like Flesch-Kincaid, Eng-Editor, and COH-Metrix thanks to the quick development of corpus linguistics and information technology. Teachers can swiftly determine the language of learning materials, especially the lexical complexity, and make necessary adjustments with the help of these technology instruments. Text modification is often necessary because the original texts are too complicated, even for EFL students. To modify reading texts, the majority of teachers rely on their subjective intuition and pedagogical experience. In addition to taking a lot of time, this procedure may result in inconsistent text authenticity, quality, and complexity levels.

“aialaia” as a Text Adapting Tool. An artificial intelligence tool called "aialaia Text Adapter" was created by the Amsterdam Center for Education and Research. This tool allows for the quantitative evaluation of difficulty levels and identifies important characteristics influencing the linguistic complexity of reading materials. The Text Adapter Tool analyzes the vocabulary and complexity of texts using sophisticated machine learning and natural language processing algorithms, then creates content versions that are appropriate for various skill levels. This tool's objective is to guarantee that all language learners can access and comprehend the learning materials. It identifies readability and lexical difficulty of the text and generates versions of the text suitable for varying levels of proficiency, ensuring comprehensibility for all students. The preservation of technical terms and

significant textual concepts is the primary distinction between "aialaia" and other AI tools like chat.gpt and gemini.

The tool appears when you click on a certain link to access the internet. The first blank field is filled with the chosen source text. The approximate word count is also supplied after the user level has been chosen. The adaption procedure is started by clicking the "Make it" button.

Figure 1. <https://www.aialaia.com/text-adapter-tool/>

It is crucial to remember that the user levels in this program are shown according to the English educational systems' grade levels. To guarantee alignment, it is wise to look at the relationship between the British National Curriculum's grade-based language levels and the international CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) standard.

Stages of education	Grades	CEFR level
Primary School	1-2 (5-7 ages)	Pre A1
	3-6 (7-11 ages)	A1 -A2
Secondary School	7-9 (11-14 ages)	A2 -B1 B1-B2

Students in grades 7-9 are projected to have A2-B1 level language competency, based on the data in the table. Additionally, the first-year math majors who

	10-11 (14-16 ages)	
Post- secondary school	12-13 (16-18 ages)	B2-C1

participate in our study have this intermediate level of language skill. Thus, when using the "Text Adapter Tool," we chose the grade levels 7, 8 and 9 adaptations. Using this technical tool not only simplified the text's content but also modified the intricate lexical units, sentence structures, and grammatical connections to fit the learners' proficiency levels, according to the comparison between the original text and the modified text displayed in the table.

Original text.

Many thousands of years ago this was a world without numbers. Nobody missed them. Primitive men knew only ten number-sounds. The reason was that they counted in the way a small child counts today, one by one, making use of their fingers. The needs and possessions of primitive men were few: they required no large numbers. When they wanted to express a number greater than ten they simply combined certain of the ten sounds connected with their fingers. Thus, if they wanted to express – one more than ten they said – one-ten and so on. Nowadays Maths has become an inseparable part of our lives and whether we work in an office or spend most of our time at home, each one of us uses Maths as a part of our everyday life. No matter where we are as well as whatever we are doing, Maths is always there whether you notice it or not. When you buy a car, follow a recipe, or decorate your home, you are using Maths principles. People have been using these same principles for thousands of years, across countries and continents. Whether you are sailing a boat off the coast of Japan or building a house in Peru, you are using Maths to get things done. Modern mathematics has spread into some interesting and incredibly useful areas of modern life. Highway engineers use optimization techniques and linear algebra to analyze traffic patterns and minimize travel time for commuters. Airlines,

hotels, and Broadway theaters (not to mention some retailers) use complex mathematical models, so complex that only computer programs can sometimes solve them, to set prices on a dynamic basis. Physicists use group theory and tensor analysis to solve the mysteries of sub-atomic particles. There are numerous other examples, from statistics being used by the Census Bureau and research firms to predict market trends, to partial differential equations being used by brokerage houses to formulate models of where the market is going. Archimedes (c.287 – 212 BC) defined the surface area and volume of a sphere and worked with infinite series, as well as contributing to the study of physics with the principle of buoyancy and the creation of the Archimedes screw, which could transfer water from one location to another (including raising it against the pull of gravity). **Total: 382 words**

Adapted text

Many years ago, people didn't have numbers like we do now. They only knew ten number-sounds and counted using their fingers. When they needed to express numbers greater than ten, they combined these sounds. Today, Math is a crucial part of our lives. Whether at work or home, we use Math every day without even realizing it. From buying a car to following a recipe, Math is always present. Modern Math is used in various fields. Math is all around us, from buying a car to decorating your home. People worldwide have used math for thousands of years. Whether sailing in Japan or building in Peru, math helps us achieve our goals. Engineers use it to analyze traffic patterns, airlines set prices using complex models, and physicists solve mysteries with Math. Archimedes, an ancient mathematician, made significant contributions to Math and physics. He defined the surface area of a sphere and worked with infinite series. **Total: 155 words**

Conclusion. Very little research has been done on the use, benefits, and drawbacks of authentic sources in ESP education; they have mostly been employed in the context of EFL instruction. Specifically, it is thought that both teachers and

students benefit equally from using real sources in ESP reading classes. However, because of their intricate language and content, these publications can also be challenging for students. Therefore, in order to accomplish the desired goal of the ESP course, the content must be adjusted to the learners' level of expertise.

References:

1. Hutchinson T. & Waters A. English for Specific Purposes. Cambridge University Press, 1994. 125 p.
2. Flowerdew J. & Peacock, M. Research perspectives on English for Academic Purposes. Cambridge University Press, 2001. 182 p.
3. Levy H. M. The Clearing House: A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas, 2008. 81 p.
4. Mishan F. Designing authenticity into language learning material. Bristol: Intellect, 2005. 40 p.
5. Reppen R. Using corpora in the language classroom. Cambridge University Press, 2010. 35-50 p.
6. Swales J. ESP: the textbook problem. The ESP Journal, 1980. 5-13 p.
7. Nunan D. The learner-centered curriculum: A study in second language teaching (4th ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1988.
8. Tomlinson B. Developing Materials for Language Teaching Second Edition. Bloomsbury Academic An. 2013.